

Methodological insights on fostering nature engagement capabilities through virtual tours

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Virtual tours of nature use 360-degree footage, both stills and videos, together with omni-directional audio captured in the setting. The footage is developed into a tour that is web-based and can be viewed on various hardware such as laptop, tablet and smartphone (Figure 1).

Virtual tours are increasingly utilised by organisations to encourage people to visit the locations that they want to promote. For example, the [Woodland Trust](#) and [Scotland360](#) both offer viewers the opportunity to experience snapshots of outdoors spaces from the comfort of their own homes.

While these ‘snapshot’ virtual tours can provide a strong overall sense of a place or space, they often encourage viewers to jump from one hotspot to another without showing the actual physical path someone would need to follow in real life. We want to understand whether virtual tours can be used to encourage people who do not usually engage with outdoor spaces, or who may have mobility challenges, to become comfortable with a place before going there. By enabling viewers to build a more complete mental model or map of the space through viewing a virtual tour, we aim to foster preparedness and capability for visiting that place in real life. As such, in this project funded through the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme project ‘Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing’, we capture the actual pathways and terrain that people would encounter were they to visit the location in real life.

During the course of our project, we have collated a series of insights which may be of interest to practitioners interested in using virtual tours to promote their outdoors spaces to a broader audience.

Figure 1 Front page of a web-based virtual tour of nature

Virtual tours are straightforward to use

Virtual tours are an intuitive and easy to operate visual communication tool. They are straightforward for a user to access and explore via the websites on which they are hosted, and links to them are easily shareable on social media.

Easy to tailor supplementary material

The ability to incorporate supplementary material (e.g. slideshows, videos, URLs, pdfs) to enrich the basic tour means that virtual tours can be tailored to meet the needs of their target audience. For example, Learning for Sustainability content could be included in a virtual tour of local green and blue spaces designed for school teachers as a resource; detailed photographs and infographics of fungi could be added to a virtual tour of a woodland for a target audience of mycologists; a virtual tour aimed at facilitating elderly and disabled access to an outdoor space could provide detailed content about path surfaces, inclines and benches.

Multiple perspectives

360° footage can be captured from multiple levels, enabling viewers to see the environment from different viewpoints. This might include ground level, eye-level or a view from above. Changing perspectives within a virtual tour offers viewers the opportunity to experience an environment from another user's perspectives, for example young children's height, or from more-than human perspectives such as small mammals, dogs and birds.

Visitor metrics

It is possible to collect a range of data through embedded tools in a virtual tour. Google Analytics can provide data on how viewers interact with a tour, including metrics such as number of views, session duration and viewer location. Viewer engagements with specific parts of the tour can also be tracked.

Feedback and citizen science updates

Virtual tour footage captures an environment at a particular moment in time, reflecting the time of day, season and weather during which it was filmed. Information about different conditions can be presented as additional content, but unpredictable changes to the environment such as fallen trees and localised flooding cannot be captured in advance. Methods for gathering material to ensure that tour content is up to date include embedding a feedback form within the tour, and/or enabling viewers to upload photographs of the current environmental situation. These methods of course require monitoring of feedback by the tour creator, so that the tour content can be updated.

Resources required

In order to produce virtual tours it is necessary to have a 360-degree camera which can be mounted on a robust monopod, and an omnidirectional microphone. A large capacity SD card is required to store the footage until the images can be downloaded. Specialist editing software is required to stitch the footage together into the tour.

The time involved in creating (and the possible subsequent updating of) virtual tours should not be underestimated. An important first step is to storyboard the tour, necessitating a visit to the area to note where and how to take the footage. Depending on the size of the area that the tour covers, capturing footage can take a number of days. Once the footage has been uploaded into virtual tour software, stitching the tour together and adding additional content is time-consuming. Time must also be allowed for piloting the tour before publication.

Technical support

Once the virtual tour is finalised, it needs to be published and hosted on a website, which is likely to require IT support from within an organisation. Updating the tour to reflect any environmental changes then becomes a non-trivial issue, again requiring IT support.

Demographic challenges

In an inclusive society virtual tours should be able to be viewed and be useful to everyone, but in order to view a virtual tour one needs access to a computer or smartphone. In addition to this digital divide, New Scots, who might benefit greatly from some virtual tours, may encounter language barriers within the tours. Finally, Generation Z (digital natives) and their successors many find the production quality of virtual tours that have not been created by computer professionals less impressive than older generations.

Acknowledgement: This work was funded by the Scottish Government's Rural and Environmental Sciences and Analytical Services (RESAS) Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027) through the project 'Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1). It corresponds to D17, submitted as part of a work package titled 'Nature engagement capabilities' (WP3).

Suggested citation: Conniff, A., Williams, A. and Irvine, K.N. (2026). *Methodological insights on fostering nature engagement capabilities through virtual tours*. Report for Scottish Government. Deliverable D17 for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1), The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20845472

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Companion report: Conniff, A., Somervail, P., Irvine, K.N. (2024). *Assessing functionality and usability of a virtual tour for nature engagement: brief report*. Report for Scottish Government. The James Hutton Institute, Scotland. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12621264

Virtual tours of nature produced under JHI-C6-1:

Virtual Tour of the Oak Path at Cashel Forest in Loch Lomond and Trossachs National Park, Scotland
<https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/cashelforestoakpath/>

Virtual Tour of Seaton Park and Donmouth in Aberdeen, Scotland
<https://virtualtours.hutton.ac.uk/SeatonDonmouth-Portal/>